

EU-DREAM

Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European
Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy
Transition and Markets

D9.1 Project Management Plan

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYMS	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEM	Demonstrator
DMP	Data Management Plan
DT	Digital Twin
EAB	Ethics and Data Protection Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EIB	Exploitation and Innovation Board
EU	European Union
EXB	Executive Board
GA	Grant Agreement
GEA	General Assembly
IAB	International Advisory Board
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LL	Living Lab
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
NLP	Natural Language Processing
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PCO	Project Coordinator
PM	Person Month
PMO	Project Management Office
PO	Project Officer
PU	Public
R	Report
RAG	Replication Advisory Group
SEN	Sensitive
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TEC	Technical Coordinator
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package

CONSORTIUM

Participant No.	Participant Organisation Name	Acronym	Country
1 (Coordinator)	Universidade do Porto	UPO	PT
2 (Partner)	Cleanwatts Digital SA	CWD	PT
3 (Partner)	EPRI Europe DAC	EEU	IE
4 (Partner)	SSE Airtricity LTD	SSEA	IE
5 (Partner)	DCSix Technologies Limited	DCS	IE
6 (Partner)	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	DK
7 (Partner)	Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY	VTT	FI
8 (Partner)	AKKA High Tech – Akkodis Group	AKKO	FR
8.1 (Affiliated)	AKKA I&S	AKKIS	FR
8.2 (Affiliated)	MODIS France	MODIS	FR
9 (Partner)	Universidad de Castilla - La Mancha	UCLM	ES
10 (Partner)	Agenzia Nazionale per le Nuove Tecnologie, L'energia e lo Sviluppo Economico Sostenibile	ENEA	IT
11 (Partner)	Consorzio Interuniversitario Nazionale per Energia e Sistemi Elettrici	ENSIEL	IT
11.1 (Affiliated)	Politecnico di Torino	POLITO	IT
11.2 (Affiliated)	Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II	UNINA	IT
11.3 (Affiliated)	Università degli Studi di Salerno	UNISA	IT
12 (Partner)	Fondazione Links - Leading Innovation & Knowledge for Society	LINKS	IT
13 (Partner)	IREN SPA	IREN	IT
13.1 (Affiliated)	IREN Mercato SPA	IME	IT
14 (Partner)	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis	AUTH	EL
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EU-DREAM project (Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets) is a 42-month Horizon Europe project focused on improving consumer interaction with the energy market. It aims to simplify complex energy management processes and enhance customer awareness, trust, and confidence through the introduction of an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based assistant and a Natural Language Processing (NLP) intermediary.

The project is divided into 9 Work Packages (WPs), with **WP9** focusing on Project Management and Coordination activities. **WP9** comprises four tasks:

- Task 9.1: Consortium Operating Procedures, Quality Assurance, Risk Management and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR);
- Task 9.2: Ethics, Data Protection and AI-based Systems Technical Robustness;
- Task 9.3: Operative, Administrative and Financial Management and Reporting;
- Task 9.4: Cooperation with European Union (EU) Projects, BRIDGE Initiative and Horizon Europe Instruments,

This is a transversal WP, led by UPO, in which all project partners participate, with a total of 45 Person/Month (PMs).

This deliverable, D9.1, provides the Project Management Plan with Gantt chart and work breakdown structure. It includes presentation standards for deliverables and reports to the EC, measures to ensure timely reporting, and guidelines for financial reporting. The risk and contingency plans are provided and will be regularly updated. This deliverable refers to Task 9.1. Updates will be considered in M14 (August 2025) and M28 (October 2026).

The EU-DREAM project is expected to significantly improve consumer interaction with the energy market, leading to increased energy efficiency and more informed, empowered energy consumers.

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Introduction

The EU-DREAM project is a 42-month Horizon Europe initiative designed to **enhance consumer interaction** with the energy market. This project aims to simplify complex energy management processes and foster customer awareness, trust, and confidence through innovative technologies, including an **Artificial Intelligence (AI)**-based assistant and a **Natural Language Processing (NLP)** intermediary. By enabling more informed and active participation in energy transitions and markets, EU-DREAM addresses critical challenges in the energy sector.

The **WP9** aims to address the **Project Management and Coordination** activities of **EU-DREAM**, following the below objectives:

- Coordinate the actions of participants and monitor the progress of project goals to ensure the delivery of results in a timely, cost-effective way;
- Financial and administrative management, being a reliable interface to the European Commission (EC), the external stakeholders and the public at large;
- Identification and mitigation of project risks by performing effective risk management and managing the project's Intellectual Property (IP).

As part of the **WP9**, this deliverable, D9.1 Project Management Plan, is a fundamental piece of addressing the WP objectives, serving as a foundational document for all the project's management and coordination efforts. The scope of D9.1 includes quality assurance and risk management, presentation standards for deliverables and reports to the EC, measures to ensure timely reporting, and guidelines for financial reporting. The risk and contingency plans are included and will be regularly updated.

Updates to this deliverable will be provided at M14 and M28 to ensure that the project management and coordination efforts remain completely aligned with the project's progress and evolving needs.

Overview of the EU-DREAM Project

EU-DREAM brings together a group of preeminent energy industry and research partners focused on accelerating innovation in **digital tools** and promoting the effective uptake of **digital services**. EU-DREAM is fully aligned with the *EU Action Plan on the Digitalisation of the Energy System* as it proposes to develop the *next generation* of energy services, solutions and products that **really work** for energy consumers. EU-DREAM has **9 Specific Objectives** (SO1-SO9):

- **SO1:** Development of **data-driven** cross-sector integrated services, solutions and products using data sources from **energy** and **non-energy sectors** that empower consumers in the energy transition, integrating all data streams into an innovative EU-DREAM data-driven federation of platforms.
- **SO2:** Development of novel **Digital Twin (DT) models** and **infrastructure** of household energy consumers that make use of profiling models to help consumers, citizens, energy suppliers, aggregators and energy communities to optimise data-driven sector-oriented services and to enhance digital energy literacy.
- **SO3:** Development of a ground-breaking **AI-based assistant tool** and **NLP-based intermediary** integrated with the DT infrastructure, providing information and suggestions to the users and allowing them to use layperson's terms to express expectations on the energy performance and cost of the household.
- **SO4:** Development of a **cloud-based data-sharing** platform for searching, accessing and using energy and non-energy-related data, ensuring **security, interoperability** and the seamless **integration** of all technical modules, and supporting social and behavioural user-centric scenarios.
- **SO5:** Development of new **AI-powered** and **simplified digital platforms** for **energy services** to empower non-experienced consumers, supplemented by an **energy marketplace** digital platform for more experienced users who can engage in peer-to-peer (P2P) physical or financial energy trading.
- **SO6:** Development of **digital visualisation** and **access tools** to allow citizens to visualise and access all the energy-related data generated, being **user-friendly** and able to adapt to the diverse requirements of trust and heterogeneous user profile types, promoting consumer interaction and engagement.
- **SO7:** Development of a set of novel **market mechanisms** for **energy** and **flexibility** to support consumers to maximally use the new digital technologies enabled by AI applications, supporting other market actors in the adoption, use and integration of digital tools.
- **SO8:** Development of novel **consumer-centric** approaches to identify the requirements for products, services and business models from a **multi-commodity** and **cross-sectorial** perspective, to support AI-powered digital tools used by consumers and citizens, assessing the impact on market efficiency.
- **SO9:** Development of **digital empowerment skills** and **energy literacy** of the end-users, intertwining new technological developments with relevant **Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) expertise** to facilitate citizens' participation in the use of the new digital tools tested in 6 Living Labs (LLs) from 6 EU countries.

The EU-DREAM project considers a total of 13 **Milestones**, as can be seen in Table 1. Moreover, Table 2 summarizes the EU-DREAM **Deliverables**. Each deliverable is associated with one task.

Table 1 EU-DREAM Milestones

Milestone No	Milestone Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date (Month)
1	System architecture design ready	WP1	12-LINKS	D1.1 and D1.2 approved	12
2	DT models and infrastructure complete	WP2-3	12-LINKS	D2.1, D2.2, D3.1 approved	15
3	AI-based assistant tool & NLP-based intermediary ready	WP2	8-AKKO	D2.3 and D2.4 approved	18
4	Cloud-based data-sharing platform ready	WP3	8-AKKO	D3.2, D3.3, D3.4 approved	18
5	Digital platforms for all users complete	WP4	14-AUTH	D4.1, D4.2, D4.3 approved	33
6	Digital visualisation and access tools complete	WP4	15-DOMX	D4.4 approved	36
7	Market and business models for energy/flexibility ready	WP5	16-VITO	D5.1 and D5.2 approved	30
8	Impact assessment of digital-AI tools uptake complete	WP5	16-VITO	D5.3 and D5.4 approved	36
9	Energy literacy empowerment results ready	WP6	14-AUTH	D6.1 and D6.2 approved	30
10	Global SSH assessment ready	WP6-7	7-VTT	D6.3, D6.4, D7.8 approved	36
11	LL results validation complete	WP7	2-CWD	D7.2-D7.7 approved	36
12	Project identity and communication material ready	WP8	3-EEU	D8.1 (initial) approved	3
13	Project Management Plan and DMP complete	WP9	1-UPO	D9.1 and D9.2 approved	6

Table 2 EU-DREAM Deliverables

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (Month)
D1.1	Survey report	WP1	11-ENSIEL	R	PU	12
D1.2	System architecture	WP1	12-LINKS	R	PU	12
D1.3	Modular platforms	WP1	8-AKKO	R	PU	15
D1.4	Use cases	WP1	10-ENEA	R	PU	18
D2.1	DT models	WP2	6-AAU	OTHER	PU	12
D2.2	DT infrastructure	WP2	12-LINKS	OTHER	PU	15
D2.3	AI-based assistant tool	WP2	12-LINKS	OTHER	PU	18
D2.4	NLP-based intermediary	WP2	8-AKKO	OTHER	PU	18

D3.1	Data management & security	WP3	12-LINKS	R	PU	15
D3.2	Data sharing interoperability	WP3	8-AKKO	OTHER	PU	15
D3.3	Data access services	WP3	8-AKKO	R	PU	18
D3.4	Data management platform	WP3	8-AKKO	OTHER	PU	18
D4.1	Digital platform design	WP4	14-AUTH	R	PU	24
D4.2	Digital platform 1	WP4	14-AUTH	R	PU	30
D4.3	Digital platform 2	WP4	14-AUTH	R	PU	33
D4.4	Digital visualization tool	WP4	15-DOMX	DEM	PU	36
D5.1	Consumer behaviour	WP5	7-VTT	R	PU	24
D5.2	Flexibility mechanisms	WP5	16-VITO	R	PU	30
D5.3	Consumer-centric approaches	WP5	9-UCLM	R	PU	33
D5.4	Impact assessment	WP5	16-VITO	R	PU	36
D6.1	Motivational drivers	WP6	7-VTT	R	PU	24
D6.2	Energy literacy empowerment	WP6	14-AUTH	R	PU	30
D6.3	Consumer responsiveness	WP6	9-UCLM	R	PU	33
D6.4	Energy policy lessons	WP6	7-VTT	R	PU	36
D7.1	LLs quality evaluation	WP7	1-UPO	R	PU	42
D7.2	LL in Portugal	WP7	2-CWD	R	PU	36
D7.3	LL in Belgium	WP7	16-VITO	R	PU	36
D7.4	LL in Italy	WP7	13-IREN	R	PU	36
D7.5	LL in Ireland	WP7	4-SSEA	R	PU	36
D7.6	LL in Greece	WP7	15-DOMX	R	PU	36
D7.7	LL in Denmark	WP7	6-AAU	R	PU	36
D7.8	SSH contributions to LLs	WP7	7-VTT	R	PU	36
D7.9	Replication Plan	WP7	2-CWD	R	PU	42
D7.10	Business Plan	WP7	2-CWD	R	SEN	42
D8.1	D&C Plan	WP8	3-EEU	R	PU	3 (14 and 28)
D8.2	Exploitation Plan	WP8	3-EEU	R	PU	42
D8.3	Recommendations	WP8	3-EEU	R	PU	42
D8.4	Final D&C activities	WP8	3-EEU	R	PU	42
D9.1	Project Management Plan	WP9	1-UPO	R	PU	3 (14 and 28)
D9.2	Data Management Plan	WP9	1-UPO	DMP	PU	6
D9.3	Cooperation activities	WP9	1-UPO	R	PU	14 (28 and 42)

Overall Structure of the Work Plan

EU-DREAM work plan (Figure 1) proposes a series of **9** logical and interrelated **WPs** over **42 months**, namely: **WP1** - Data-Driven Cross-Sector Integrated Services, Solutions and Products; **WP2** - Digital Twin, AI-based Assistant Tool and NLP-based Intermediator; **WP3** - Data-Sharing Infrastructure, Security and Interoperability; **WP4** - Digital Platforms, Tools and Technologies for Energy Services; **WP5** - Market Design for Digital Tools Uptake and Flexibility Services; **WP6** - Social Innovation, Consumers' Digital Empowerment and Energy Literacy; **WP7** - Living Labs, SSH Intertwining, Replicability and Business Innovation; **WP8** - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication; **WP9** - Project Management and Coordination.

Figure 1 EU-DREAM work plan with 9 interrelated WPs

EU-DREAM has **3 well-balanced Phases**:

- **Phase 1** (M1-M18) with 158 PMs – Data-driven cross-sector services, solutions, products (**WP1**); DT, AI-based assistant tool and NLP-based intermediary (**WP2**); Data sharing, security, interoperability (**WP3**).
- **Phase 2** (M13-M36) with 159 PMs – Digital tools, platforms and energy data visualisation (**WP4**); Energy and flexibility markets (**WP5**); Digital empowerment, energy literacy and social innovation tools (**WP6**).
- **Phase 3** (M10-M42) with 150 PMs – Demonstration and validation with 6 LLs in 6 EU countries, including scalability/replicability, go-to-market strategy, Business Plan, intertwining SSH contributions with LLs (**WP7**).

Also, **WP8** (45 PMs) and **WP9** (45 PMs) handle dissemination, exploitation and communication, and project management, respectively. The timing of the different WPs and their components is provided in Figure 2, while the graphical presentation of the components showing how they inter-relate is provided in Figure 3.

Figure 2 EU-DREAM GANTT Chart

Figure 3 EU-DREAM PERT Chart

Organisational Structure

EU-DREAM consortium brings together **22 participants** (16 beneficiaries, 6 affiliated entities) from 9 EU countries, providing **complementarity** based on **interdisciplinary** knowledge. The 6 LLs in 6 EU countries provide the **critical infrastructure** needed to carry out the project activities. These LLs and their peculiarities will demonstrate the general applicability of the highly modular and adjustable **innovative solutions** of EU-DREAM, serving as *lighthouses* to derive broad replicable schemes, guidelines and *blueprints* in line with *REPowerEU* and the *Clean Energy Package*. The extension of the consortium (and also of the LLs) across multiple **climatic conditions** and **geographic regions** allows project results to be based on a very **wide range** of regulatory environments, and societal and cultural backgrounds.

The **Project Coordinator** (PCO), UPO, is the legal entity acting as the liaison between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The PCO shall execute the tasks allocated to it as depicted in the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA). The organization of WPs and Tasks aims to coordinate, monitor, and report on the progress of the work plan for the related WP and task, respectively. More specifically, **WP Leaders** prepare and direct plans for the WP tasks and report the tasks advancements to the PCO. The PCO is supported by 4 interacting bodies (Figure 4):

- **General Assembly** (GEA), is the decisive decision-making body, comprising one representative person per partner. It is responsible for the approval of the management structure and the project direction.
- **Executive Board** (EXB), composed of all WP leaders (11-ENSIEL, 12-LINKS, 8-AKKO, 14-AUTH, 16-VITO, 7-VTT, 2-CWD, 3-EEU), including the PCO that leads the WP9, and the Technical Coordinator (TEC), 2-CWD, that leads the WP7. This is the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, accountable to the GEA.
- **Exploitation and Innovation Board** (EIB), co-chaired by the TEC, 2-CWD, composed of all LL leaders (16-VITO, 13-IREN, 4-SSEA, 15-DOMX, 6-AAU) and 3-EEU (that leads the WP8). IPR strategy tasks are managed by the EIB. Also, the CA governs IPR management rules.
- **Project Management Office** (PMO), who is accountable for managing the financial and administrative aspects of the project. This is the Research and Innovation Support Unit of UPO.

An **International Advisory Board** (IAB) was built with external experts from academia and industry, appointed and guided by the EXB. The IAB will provide contributions to the GEA decisions. The PCO will guarantee that a non-disclosure agreement (NDA) is completed by any IAB member, to safeguard Confidential Information that may be unveiled by any partner to any IAB member, directly or indirectly by the PCO. Current IAB members are shown in Table 3. Teleconference meetings with the IAB members are expected to occur at least once per year.

An **Ethics and Data Protection Advisory Board** (EAB) will monitor and address ethics questions, user interaction, data, and AI-based systems issues in EU-DREAM, composed of the following partners: 12-LINKS (Leader), 8-AKKO, 6-AAU, 10-ENEA, 4-SSEA, and 7-VTT. Also, a **Replication Advisory Group** (RAG) will monitor and foster replication, composed of the following partners: 2-CWD (Leader), 15-DOMX, 4-SSEA, 13-IREN, 16-VITO, and 3-EEU, in close collaboration with all the IAB members to foster replication beyond the consortium.

Figure 4 Overall organisation structure of EU-DREAM

Table 3 International Advisory Board Members

Name	Institution	Country
Bikash Pal	Imperial College London	UK
Nermin Suljanović	Elektroinstitut Milan Vidmar	Slovenia
Venizelos Efthymiou	EPL Technology Frontiers Ltd	Cyprus
Nikolaos Chatziargyriou	National Technical University of Athens	Greece
Miguel Asensio	ENGIE Energy International	Spain
Alexandra Revez	University College Cork	Ireland
Tim O’Callaghan	Electric Corby Community Interest Company	UK
Antonio Iliceto	TERNA S.P.A.	Italy
Christina Papadimitriou	Eindhoven University of Technology	Netherlands

A strategic objective of the project consists of implementing the EU-DREAM approach across the different LLs. For this reason, the WP7 Leader (which is also the TEC, 2-CWD) is responsible for the coordination and monitoring of activities related to the **EU-DREAM LLs**. The TEC reports to the PCO about the advancement of the work done in each LL, mainly underlining possible delays on the agreed plan or issues.

In terms of **voting rules**, each Consortium Body should not deliberate and determine meetings validly without 2/3 of its Members being present or represented (quorum). If the quorum is not achieved, the chairperson shall organise another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. Each Member of a Consortium Body present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote. Decisions shall be taken by a majority of 2/3 of the votes cast. Full details regarding the decision-making mechanism, veto rights, voting rules, and quorum, are provided in the GA.

The overall **schedule management** of EU-DREAM is carried out by the PCO. The action plan inside each WP (and task) is handled by its respective leader. As the **monthly monitoring** is accomplished, eventual delays should be identified, reported to the PCO and corrected, getting the project back on track.

For **variances** (delays in terms of due dates) greater than 1 month, the WP leader should directly inform the PCO. Variances greater than 2 months are considered not acceptable. WP leaders should immediately notify the PCO if any milestones are at risk of being unattained. The same regarding the due date of the deliverables.

Risk Management

Risk Management consists of recognizing, evaluating and ranking potential risks to soften the likelihood and/or severity of these inappropriate events. Risk-mitigation measures with appropriate contingency plans should be adequately proposed to diminish the impact of these risks.

Table 4 presents the potential risks identified in EU-DREAM, their likelihood and severity, and also the proposed **risk-mitigation measures**. This table will be constantly updated as the project progresses. Since the project has just started, the risks are those reported in the GA. However, the Risk Register will report progressively any new risks identified during the project lifecycle.

Table 4 Risk description and proposed risk-mitigation measures

Risk No	Description	Likelihood	Severity	WP No	Proposed Risk-Mitigation Measures
1	Information required in all data-intensive tasks may not become promptly available.	High	Medium	WP1, WP3	Similar data (e.g. from former projects) will be promptly identified and monitored.
2	Low rate of consumers' involvement in data provision.	Medium	High	WP1, WP5	Redundant number and types of consumers and continuous search for new consumers.
3	Consumer data may not be available in time or not be detailed enough.	Medium	Medium	WP2, WP3	Upfront alignment between different WPs on data expectations from consumers.
4	Digital tools to be developed fail to meet user requirements and functionalities.	Low	High	WP2, WP4	The majority of project partners and specifically the LLs leaders are also part of WP4.
5	Misalignment between digital platforms development and market models.	Medium	Medium	WP4, WP5	Partners from WP5 are also part of WP4 to ensure alignment between developments.
6	Models available may not be sufficient to quantify consumer involvement impact.	Medium	Low	WP5, WP6	EU-DREAM has engaged multiple partners with extensive quantitative modelling skills.

7	IoT protocol interoperability issues arise from component vendors.	High	Medium	WP7	EU-DREAM is based on widely adopted protocols to achieve interoperability.
8	Changes in regulation and policies may affect digital platform design.	Low	Medium	WP4, WP5	Continuous monitoring of regulations and policies will ensure adaptive development.
9	Business adoption of EU-DREAM results is not as expected.	Medium	Medium	WP8	The Exploitation Plan will be elaborated early in the project, to be improved continuously.
10	A limited number of relevant stakeholders are involved in the project.	Medium	High	WP8	Contacts with relevant stakeholders will be carried out from the beginning of the project.
11	Low replication and scalability of the project.	Low	High	WP7	EU-DREAM supports upscaling initiatives, including replicability in diverse areas.
12	Low visibility of the project.	Low	Medium	WP8	The team is integrated into extensive networks at local, national and international levels.
13	Partner leaving the EU-DREAM consortium.	Low	High	WP9	Responsibilities will be redistributed across existing partners or looking for a new one.
14	Loss of key staff and rehiring Delays.	Medium	Low	WP9	New personnel are swiftly integrated through interconnected communication with partners.
15	Weak commitment of a partner or lack of coordination between partners.	Medium	Low	WP9	The management structure is defined to cover lack of commitment and miscommunication.
16	The delay of one of the WPs can affect the others.	Low	Medium	WP9	WP leaders' regular meetings are used for everyone to know the status of all WPs.

The duty of handling the **project risks** relies on the PCO. The risks are recognised and addressed in terms of two major aspects in this project: likelihood and severity. The monitoring of the currently identified risks and the new potential risks is carried out by the PCO in strict cooperation with all WP leaders. Accordingly, a Risk Register will be kept by the PCO and the WP leaders, being constantly analysed in every consortium meeting and updated according to the evolution of the project.

During the consortium meetings, under WP9, the risks are assessed as a regular agenda item. If any change is reported, either in terms of likelihood or severity, or if any new risk is detected, the **Risk Register** will be revised, and the proper risk-management measures will also be adapted appropriately.

Quality Management

Quality management in EU-DREAM aims to assure a very high quality in the deliverables of the project ahead of being submitted to the EC. Hence, a rigorous quality management process is implemented for the deliverables to guarantee that all WPs are performed with the highest technical quality level, including timelines, internal thorough review processes, and regular quality checks. Quality management includes topics connected to self-assessment and peer review, assuring also that all ethical concerns are safeguarded.

Quality management is carried out under the responsibility of the PCO, ensuring that the deliverables are timely, exhaustive, clear and effective. The PCO works closely with:

- The WP leaders, who are co-responsible for the quality check at both scientific and technical levels of all deliverables in that WP.
- The Project Officer (PO), acting on behalf of the EC, who provides guidance and recommendations on every quality issue regarding the deliverables.

The **monitoring process** must predict potential issues related to the progress of tasks and the creation of deliverables. Each WP leader should report the developments and eventual delays in deliverables creation during the WP meetings every month. The **quality assurance** procedure for the deliverables in EU-DREAM is outlined below:

- **Initial Draft:** The WP leader and the Task/Delivery leader structure the first ideas of the deliverable, assign contributions to partners and suggest deadlines. A preliminary Table of Contents (ToC) should be circulated at least **4 weeks** in advance of the due date.
- **Consolidation:** The WP leader and the Task/Delivery leader collect and consolidate all the relevant inputs from the partners contributing to the deliverable.
- **Final Draft:** The consolidated version is ready for internal review. The document should be ready at least **3 weeks** before delivery date.
- **Peer Review:** Review by a minimum of two internal project members, evaluating the scientific content, language, and readability. The role is to provide detailed feedback to the report and constructive comments for its improvement. The review should be done at least **2 weeks** before the delivery date.
- **Final Editing:** Formatting, editing and incorporation of review comments by the Task/Delivery leader. The document should be updated at least **1 week** before the delivery date, corresponding to the release candidate version.
- **Quality Check:** The ultimate quality check is performed by the PCO ahead of the submission process, including proofreading, conformance with the template formatting styles, correctness of references, completeness of front page formal details, readability, and degree of completeness concerning what is expected according to the GA.
- **Submission:** Submission of the deliverable's final version by the PCO to the EC.

The **responsibility** for the Deliverables lies in both the WP leader and the Task/Delivery leader. All deliverables should be prepared on a timely basis, being assessed by at least two reviewers (preferably not involved in the task) before being uploaded in the portal. A total of 5 working days is considered for receiving the review comments. The Task/Delivery leader is in charge of updating the document following the review process. The PCO constantly monitors the process.

The **quality control** process for the deliverables should consider the following aspects:

- The contributions of the deliverable to the WP should be clearly stated.
- The deliverable objectives should be unambiguously identified.
- The deliverable should be a self-contained document.
- The deliverable contents should be coherent with the GA.
- The deliverable should be cohesive and concise (as much as possible).
- The deliverable should not include any unproven or unsupported claims.
- Plagiarism and self-plagiarism are simply and totally unacceptable.

To facilitate the **quality check**, each deliverable must contain:

- A title page.
- Document information.
- Document history.
- Acronyms.
- Executive summary.
- Table of Contents.
- List of Figures.
- List of Tables.
- Introduction.
- Main sections.
- Conclusion.
- References.
- Appendix, if applicable.

Moreover, all members should embrace the next practice for **writing reports**:

- Utilize the template available in the repository of EU-DREAM.
- Considered UK English all over the document.
- Carefully consider the text formatting corresponding to the given template.
- List all the acronyms.
- Use the captions for figures and tables. The caption must be added by using the MS Word "Insert Caption" functionality in the "Reference menu" using the automatic numeration. The caption has to be placed below the figures and above the tables.
- Insert references into the text using the "Insert Citation" functionality in the "Reference tab" of MS Word.
- Check the accessibility of the link inserted in the text and the references.
- Check the resolution of figures (high resolutions are preferable) in the document, making sure they are clear and readable.

Once completed the **document**, the authors should:

- Create the ToC through the "Table of Contents" functionality.
- Create the list of figures through the "Insert Table of Figures" functionality.
- Create the list of tables through the "Insert Table of Figures" functionality and then select "Table" as a "Caption label" functionality.

A **document** in EU-DREAM should be produced according to the subsequent states:

- ToC, v0.1, providing the document's organization.
- First Draft, v0.2, a still unfinished version, but close to completion.
- Consolidated, v0.3, 1st complete draft that will be subject to the peer review process.
- Revision, v0.4, after the two (minimum) peer reviews are duly concluded.
- Release Candidate, v0.5, after the peer-reviewers' comments, suggestions and corrections have been implemented.
- Final Version, v1.0, when the PCO finally approves it, after the ultimate quality check, is now ready to be uploaded in the portal.

These states above should appear in the document history section. Eventually, it is possible to consider v1.1 and any following versions to represent additional improvements. After delivery, the deliverable goes through an iteration of approval by the EC. In this period, the **status** of the deliverable changes under the following stages:

- Submitted.
- Accepted.
- Accepted with remarks.
- Rejected.

The PowerPoint **presentation templates** are also available in the Consortium SharePoint. This template must be implemented for each presentation within the project, in addition to other presentations such as conferences, workshops, etc., all tied to EU-DREAM.

Project Communication and Meetings

The PCO is liable for the project **communication** linking EU-DREAM and the PO. The communication within EU-DREAM relies mainly on e-mails (using appropriate mailing lists), conference calls (Teams or Zoom are generally used), and face-to-face meetings as occurred in the kick-off meeting. Telephone calls are used mainly for urgent matters.

Hence, the main channel of **communication** in EU-DREAM is the e-mail. The EU-DREAM mailing list is maintained and constantly updated by the PCO, who regularly informs all partners regarding any potential changes. If a person should be removed or added to the mailing list, the corresponding partner should immediately contact the PCO to update it. To avoid spending unnecessary budget on travel, conference calls can surely be used, which should be scheduled in advance and follow a set agenda.

The chairperson of a Consortium Body should provide written **notice of a meeting** to every member no later than the min. number of days prior to the meeting as presented next:

- GEA: 45 calendar days for an ordinary meeting; and 15 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting.
- EXB: 14 calendar days for an ordinary meeting; 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting.

The **agenda** is a very useful tool for ensuring the smooth running of the meeting and obtaining the required information. The text of the email that accompanies the agenda should highlight the eventual requests of the chairperson to the participants. The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall prepare and send each member an agenda no later than the min. number of days prior to the meeting as presented next:

- GEA: 21 calendar days; 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting.
- EXB: 7 calendar days.

Any member of a Consortium Body may **attach an item** to the previous agenda by written notice to all members no later than the min. number of days prior to the meeting as presented next:

- GEA: 14 calendar days, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting.
- EXB: 2 calendar days.

The chairperson of a Consortium Body should make **minutes** of the meetings. The draft minutes should be delivered to all members within 10 calendar days. The minutes are considered as “accepted” if, within 15 calendar days from the reception, no member has expressed any opposition or concern by written notice to the chairperson.

Regularly scheduled **conference calls** are the principal way of communication in the WPs, held at least **once per month**, to guarantee that all WP members are notified of current developments, progress on tasks, and deliverables. If possible, a fixed day of the week and time are chosen to make things easier in the scheduling of the calls. At least one member from each partner should participate in the WP conference calls. During the call, WP Leaders are in charge of directing the activities. The PCO will also try to attend all meetings himself. If necessary, WP Leaders can arrange additional conference calls beyond the agreed fixed schedule.

Regular **face-to-face project meetings** with all partners are programmed to occur on a **3-month** basis so that the entire team can exchange ideas and experiences. These project meetings are accommodated by a distinct partner every time. The possibility of having **hybrid meetings** (simultaneous face-to-face and teleconference) instead of just purely face-to-face project meetings, is also considered. Additional meetings to foster cooperation between WPs can be considered when needed.

A **project management platform** (Appendix 1) has already been defined in M1 to allow secure and private access to all the necessary documentation for the project, including remote storage and file version control. All presentations should be uploaded into this project management platform (which is a **shared repository**) right after a meeting, allowing the whole team to maintain a trace of what has been discussed and agreed upon in that meeting.

The EU-DREAM project **website** will be one of the major tools for disseminating the project's accomplishments, granting guests widespread knowledge about its goals. **Social media** accounts are already available, as follows:

- Twitter: https://x.com/eudream_project
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-dream/>

Project Periodic Report

Project reporting is the procedure employed by the EC to evaluate and monitor the financed projects. It is of major significance since it can directly condition the image of the consortium and the evaluation of the project by the EC. **Two project periodic reports** are foreseen, in M14 and M28, and they must be presented within 60 days.

Project reporting is under the accountability of the entire consortium, and every single partner should be deeply immersed in it. The PCO is in charge of collecting all the material from the partners and joining all information into the document before transferring it to the EC. Moreover, each WP leader should prepare a yearly report that includes detailed information about the advances in its activities, the milestones and the deliverables, and the fulfilment of the promised developments as per the GA.

The **financial status** of the project must also be reported to the EC by preparing financial statements to claim for the payment. The procedure to be followed is:

- The PCO asks the partners to produce their financial statements in the Participant Portal. It is a formulary that officially states the costs encountered within a particular period.
- Each partner completes the financial statements with the costs encountered during that particular period.
- Each partner submits and digitally signs the financial statement.
- The PCO submits the financial report to the EC.

Conclusion

EU-DREAM project is set to play a pivotal role in transforming consumer interaction with the energy market through innovative digital solutions. The D9.1 Project Management Plan, as outlined in this report, lays the foundation for effective project management and coordination efforts during the project's duration.

The continuous monitoring and updating of this plan will be crucial for adapting the project's progress and ensuring that its objectives—enhancing consumer awareness, trust, and participation in energy transition—are fully realized. Therefore, an update of this deliverable will be provided at M14 (August 2025) and M28 (October 2026).

Ultimately, the EU-DREAM project aims to empower consumers, foster energy efficiency, and contribute to a more informed and proactive energy market across Europe.

References

1. Twitter: EU-DREAM: https://x.com/eudream_project
2. LinkedIn: EU-DREAM: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-dream/>
3. EU-DREAM Grant Agreement 101160614
4. EU-DREAM Consortium Agreement

Appendix

Appendix 1 Project Management Platform

Horizon_EU-Dream

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Documentos

Em canais

Na biblioteca do site

Nome	Modificado	Modificado por	+ Adicionar coluna
General	3 de julho	José Luis Malaquias	
WP1_Public	8 de julho	José Luis Malaquias	
WP2_Public	8 de julho	José Luis Malaquias	
WP3_Public	8 de julho	José Luis Malaquias	
WP4_Public	8 de julho	José Luis Malaquias	
WP5_Public	8 de julho	José Luis Malaquias	
WP6_Public	8 de julho	José Luis Malaquias	
WP7_Public	8 de julho	José Luis Malaquias	
WP8_Public	8 de julho	José Luis Malaquias	
WP9_Public	8 de julho	José Luis Malaquias	

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Documentos > WP9_Public

Nome	Modificado	Modificado por
Deliverables	1 de agosto	João Catalão
General	1 de agosto	João Catalão
Meetings	1 de agosto	João Catalão
T9.1	1 de agosto	João Catalão
T9.2	1 de agosto	João Catalão
T9.3	1 de agosto	João Catalão
T9.4	1 de agosto	João Catalão
Add-Members.bat	15 de julho	José Luis Malaquias
WP_Members.csv	19 de julho	José Luis Malaquias
WP_Members.xlsx	24 de julho	Amedeo Buonanno